

Metrics to quantify performance, energy and CO₂ footprint of CMIP7 simulations.

Instructions for Modelling Centres, prepared by the Energy Consumption and Carbon Footprint Task Team.

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Background

Climate simulations are becoming increasingly complex, with each CMIP phase introducing more sophisticated models, a greater number of experiments, and larger ensembles, leading to a continuous rise in computational requirements. These simulations rely on some of the world's most powerful supercomputers, which consume energy to reproduce the Earth's climate. Yet, efforts to systematically quantify the computational cost, energy use, and environmental impact of CMIP activities have so far been limited. [The Energy Consumption and Carbon Footprint Task Team](#) was established to address this gap by measuring and reporting these aspects for the upcoming CMIP phase, CMIP7.

The Computational Performance for Model Intercomparison Project (CPMIP) defines a standardised set of metrics for evaluating Earth System Models (ESMs) and their execution on high-performance computing (HPC) platforms. These metrics were originally described in [Balaji et al. \(2017\)](#) and provide a framework to characterise climate model experiments in a consistent and comparable way. Most of the CPMIP metrics relate to runtime performance (e.g., throughput, computational cost, coupling, I/O) for a given model configuration (e.g., resolution, complexity, parallelisation).

For CMIP7, participating modelling centres are now asked to report energy consumption, which enables the estimation of the carbon footprint associated with running climate model experiments. Modelling centres participating in CMIP7 are asked to provide these metrics for the experiments they are running for the Assessment Fast Track (AFT) and community MIPs. Similar work was conducted for CMIP6 ([M.C. Acosta et al., 2024](#)), providing valuable lessons for this next phase.

While many activities contribute to the overall CO₂ emissions of CMIP projects including running simulations on HPC platforms, storing and transferring data, ESGF replication, analysis, travelling and commuting for project meetings, and managing the life cycle of computing infrastructure, the current effort focuses only on **emissions directly related to computing the simulations**.

Through the inclusion of the [Power Usage Effectiveness](#) (PUE) factor, the estimates will also account for the energy overheads of the HPC facility, such as cooling, networking, and power distribution. However, data storage, data transfers, and other offline processes are not included in this phase of the analysis. The emissions from computing the simulations, together with the infrastructure overheads captured via PUE, are expected to represent a substantial share of CMIP's total energy use. These are areas where CPMIP metrics are most relevant and where modelling centres can consistently provide data. Ongoing work aims to incorporate other emission sources in future assessments.

To promote consistent and widespread collection of experiment-level metrics by modelling centres in CMIP7, they have been organised into three tiers, reflecting both the effort required to obtain them and their analytical value.

- **Tier 1 (strongly recommend)** metrics contain the minimum information required to assess the energy consumption, computational cost, and carbon footprint of the experiments.
- **Tier 2 (encouraged)** metrics provide the additional information to analyse and interpret Tier 1 results, including basic model configuration and performance indicators to facilitate comparison across institutions and HPC machines.

- **Tier 3 (optional)** metrics offer a deeper understanding of model and system behaviour through more detailed performance indicators, which help to identify bottlenecks and improve cross-platform comparability.

In addition to these three-tier metrics requested for each experiment, **general information** will also be asked regarding the centre providing the data, the machine used, and the energy source. These additional metrics are defined at the modelling group or platform level and therefore will only need to be provided once. Following the previous approach, part of this information will be strongly encouraged to ensure a minimum level of analysis, while other elements will be optional.

Where provision of these metrics are not possible due to existing contractual obligations (e.g. HPC provision by commercial company) or the model output data is considered sensitive, please contact the Task Team at energy-carbon-questionnaire@wcrp-cmip.org to discuss.

Targeted CMIP7 simulations

We propose to collect metrics across three categories of simulations carried out by modelling centres that participate in the CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track and community MIPs:

1. **Production simulations:** Runs that generated datasets for scientific analysis, directly linked to one CMIP7 experiment, whether they were published on ESGF or not.
2. **Tuning simulations:** Runs performed during the calibration and development of the model, not meant for direct publication.
3. **Discarded simulations:** Runs that were interrupted, failed, or ultimately not used due to bugs. These simulations were thought to be in production but ended up not being used because of unexpected issues after running them.

By distinguishing these categories, we aim to capture the full range of computational effort invested in CMIP7, as well as to quantify their individual impact.

Collection, Timeline, and Dissemination of the metrics

This document introduces all metrics and specifies how they are to be collected, serving as a guideline to assist centres in collecting and reporting their data consistently.

An online spreadsheet will be distributed to all modelling institutes (one per institute). The spreadsheet will request the values of the metrics defined in this document. The information collected through the individual modelling institute spreadsheet will be compiled into a secure document maintained by BSC (Barcelona Supercomputing Centre) and – depending on the agreed data sharing policy – made available to participating modelling institutes. This shared dataset will serve as the foundation for subsequent analysis, intercomparison and reporting activities.

A dedicated [FAQ](#) page will accompany the spreadsheet to address common questions and provide clarifications. The FAQ will be maintained by the Energy Consumption and Carbon Footprint Task Team (TT) updated as new questions arise, ensuring that responses are available across all institutes.

Modelling institutes are encouraged to reach out at any time for assistance or clarification of the metrics, please contact: energy-carbon-questionnaire@wcrp-cmip.org

Timeline

The initial collection phase will cover CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track (AFT) simulations. Confirmation by the modelling centres that they can access the spreadsheet and understand the information required by early **February 2026**.

A **first round** of data collection is anticipated **by September 2026**, aiming to support downstream activities for the IPCC AR7 process, which targets historical and scenario (MIP) data availability by Summer 2026.

A second phase will extend to the broader CMIP7 MIPs, with detailed timelines to be defined once those experiments are scheduled. Due to the nature of the collection, we expect the involvement of modelling institutes to be a continuous process rather than a one-time effort, extending throughout the full CMIP7 life cycle.

Dissemination

The results derived from this activity will be disseminated through a peer-reviewed publication, and public visualisations and summaries of key statistics, similar to [ESGF Data Statistics](#) acknowledging participating modelling groups. The person(s) responsible at each institute for providing the metrics will be invited to participate in the writing or review of the publication as a co-author, contributing to the analysis of the results.

The metrics

General information

1. Modelling group (**strongly recommend**)
 - 1.1. Name.
 - 1.2. Location (city and country).
2. HPC Platform Information (**strongly recommend**)
 - 2.1. Platform name.
 - 2.2. [Power Usage Effectiveness](#) (PUE): A metric of a supercomputer's energy efficiency.
3. Emission Factor (**strongly recommend**)
 - 3.1. For the energy used by the computing centre, the carbon dioxide emissions produced per unit of a specific energy source (unit: kg CO₂/MWh).
Recommendation: Use grid averages from the most recent calendar year.
4. Energy Mix (**encouraged**)

HPC site-specific energy mix, expressed as the percentage share of primary energy sources (e.g., coal, natural gas, nuclear, hydro, wind, solar). Provide at least one of the following:

 - 4.1. A reference or official source for the HPC site's energy mix data.
 - 4.2. The actual energy mix values (raw percentages for each energy source).
Recommendation: Use averaged values over the most recent full calendar year. If site-specific data are not available, please indicate the geographic location of the HPC infrastructure (city, region or country).

Tier 1 (strongly recommend)

1. Experiment information:
 - 1.1. Experiment type: Indicate whether the simulation corresponds to a production, tuning, or discarded run.
 - 1.2. For production experiments: Specify the community-accepted experiment name as defined in the CMIP7 [experiment table](#) 'Experiments' tab.
 - 1.3. Model type: coupled, atm only, ocean only, etc.
2. Simulated Years: The number of simulated years for the experiment (unit: years)

3. Core-Hours: number of CPU core-hours consumed by the experiment, i.e. the number of cores used to run the model multiplied by the elapsed time of the run (unit: core-hours)
4. Data Output: Volume of scientific data produced by the experiment saved on the HPC disk, even if only temporarily and not permanently stored afterwards (unit: gigabytes)
5. Energy Consumption: Energy consumed by the experiment job (unit: megajoules).
 - 5.1. Preferred measurement: Hardware counters (e.g., Intel RAPL or IPMI via Baseboard Management Controller (BMC) for CPUs, NVIDIA's NVML library or ROCm-SMI for GPUs)
 - 5.2. Requirements
 - 5.2.1. Specify the data source and methodology used. This includes whether the value comes from direct node measurement (i.e., power meter), hardware counters, scheduler-level accounting, or estimation.
 - 5.2.2. Report dynamic energy, i.e., energy consumed solely by the application workload. Idle (static) energy must be excluded.
 - 5.2.3. Report total energy, i.e., energy consumed by the application plus idle energy.

Prioritising hardware counters ensures available, high-resolution, workload-specific measurements that allow for fairer comparisons across different HPC sites. Where counters are not available, other methods may be used, provided the methodology is clearly documented.

Tier 2 (encouraged)

1. SYPD (Simulated Years Per Day): Number of model years simulated per 24 hours of wall-clock run time (unit: years/day).
2. QSYPD (Queue SYPD): Simulated years per day including both queue time and run time (unit: years/day).
3. RSYPD (Real SYPD): Simulated years per day including queue time, run time, system interruptions, and workflow errors (unit: years/day).
4. Parallelisation: Number of CPU cores used for the simulation (unit: cores). Include the number of GPUs when applicable (e.g., 1000 cores + 20 GPUs).

5. Data Output Intensity: Data volume produced per compute hour (unit: GB/core-hour), including all output generated during the simulation e.g. scientifically valuable data, restarts, logs, temporary files, etc. Easily obtained by checking the runtime directory size before and after the run, divided by the number of core-hours consumed:

$$\text{Data Intensity} = \text{Output Volume [GB]} / \text{CoreHours}$$

6. Number of Grid Points: The total number of 3D grid points used in the model integrations (unit: digit).

Tier 3 (optional)

1. Complexity: Number of prognostic variables (unit: digit)
 - 1.1. For multi-component models, complexity is the sum of the prognostic variables across all components
 - 1.2. If the value is not directly known for a component or model, it can be approximated using the restart file size and Resolution:

$$\text{Complexity} = Sc/Gc/8$$

Where Sc = restart file size (bytes), Gc = number of grid points, and 8 = bytes per variable (assuming double precision)

2. Data Output Cost: Performance overhead due to the I/O (unit: ratio).
 - 2.1. Re-run the same experiment with the I/O deactivated to obtain the Core Hours per Simulated Year (CHSY) without I/O ($CHSY_without_io$)
 - 2.2. Compute Data Output Cost as:

$$\text{Data Output Cost} = 1 - \frac{CHSY_without_io}{CHSY}$$

3. Coupling Cost: Ratio of the computational overhead due to coupling and load imbalance (unit: ratio)
 - 3.1. Concurrent coupling: If the different components run on separate cores in parallel (i.e. concurrent coupling, external coupler, Multiple Program Multiple Data), this is computed as the ratio between the sum of the individual components' standalone core-hours

(*core_hours_standalone*) divided by the core-hours spent by the coupled simulation (*core_hours_coupled*):

$$\text{Coupling cost} = 1 - \frac{\sum_C \text{core_hours_standalone}_C}{\text{core_hours_coupled}}$$

3.2. Sequential coupling: If the different components run on the same cores one after the other (i.e. sequential coupling, integrated coupling framework, Single Program Multiple Data), this is approximated as the extra parallelisation required to maintain the same throughput as in a concurrent setup (i.e., the sum of each component's parallelisation so that all achieve the same throughput). Note: this requires knowing the scalability curve of the standalone components.

4. Memory Bloat: Ratio of actual memory size to the ideal memory use (unit: ratio)

4.1. Measure the runtime memory usage (*Mr*), often called 'Resident Set Size' (RSS)

4.2. Estimate memory devoted to instructions (*Mi*) as executable file size x number of processes

4.3. Approximate ideal memory size (*Mo*) using the combined size of all restart files (sum across components)

4.4. The Memory Bloat is then computed as follows:

$$\text{Memory Bloat} = \frac{(Mr - Mi)}{Mo}$$

Annex

Computing the Number of grid points

This section describes how to compute the number of grid points depending on the horizontal grid type. In all cases, the total number of 3D grid points is obtained by multiplying the number of horizontal grid points by the number of vertical levels (N_z). Please note, not all possible use-cases are covered and most modelling centres will know how to get these numbers.

1. Regular latitude–longitude / regular (full) Gaussian grid

A full Gaussian grid with N latitude lines from pole to equator (so $2N$ total latitude circles) has $4N$ longitudes at each latitude. Each latitude circle contains $4N$ equally spaced longitude points.

1.1 Horizontal grid points:

$$N_{\text{horiz}} = 8N^2$$

1.2 Total 3D grid points:

$$N_{\text{total}} = N_{\text{horiz}} \times N_z$$

Where N is the number of latitude lines between the pole and the equator.

1.3 Source: <https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/OIFS/1+Gaussian+grids>

2. Reduced Gaussian grid

A reduced Gaussian grid retains the same $2N$ latitude circles as the full Gaussian grid, but the number of longitude points decreases toward the poles. As a result, the total number of horizontal grid points cannot be expressed as a simple product of latitude and longitude counts, as it depends on the method used for reducing the grid. For each latitude circle i , the grid definition provides the corresponding number of longitude points N_i . These values are typically available in the model grid description or metadata.

2.1 $N_{\text{horiz}} = \sum N_i$, for $i=1 \dots 2N$

2.2 $N_{\text{total}} = N_{\text{horiz}} \times N_z$

3. Octahedral reduced Gaussian grid

The octahedral grid is a specific type of reduced Gaussian grid with a regular and well-defined reduction pattern.

For an octahedral grid with N latitude lines between the pole and the equator, the number of longitude points at latitude circle i (counting from the pole) is:

3.1 longitudes at latitude $i=4i+16$

Summing this over all latitude circles yields a total of horizontal grid points:

$$3.2 \text{ N}_{\text{horiz}} = 4N(N+9)$$

Total 3D grid points:

$$3.3 \text{ N}_{\text{total}} = \text{N}_{\text{horiz}} \times \text{N}_z$$

Where N is the number of latitude lines between the pole and the equator.

3.4 Source: <https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/OIFS/2+Octahedral+grid>

4. Icosahedral grids

Icosahedral grids are derived from a spherical icosahedron through successive refinements. An R_nB_m grid combines an initial root refinement (n) with m bisection steps.

4.1 Horizontal grid points:

$$\text{N}_{\text{horiz}} = 20 \times n^2 \times 4^m$$

4.2 Total 3D grid points:

$$\text{N}_{\text{total}} = \text{N}_{\text{horiz}} \times \text{N}_z$$

Where n is the root refinement (or subdivision), and m is the number of bisections

4.3 Source: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2017MS001242>

Energy profiling

Energy consumption can be divided into two components:

1. Static (Idle) Energy: Power drawn by a system when it is powered on but not performing any meaningful computation.
2. Dynamic (Workload-Dependent) Energy: Additional energy consumed as a direct result of executing the application workload.

For CMIP7, we are **specifically requesting dynamic energy measurements**, which reflect the computational cost of the climate simulation itself. To determine this, it is necessary to first quantify

the static energy, either from known idle values or by running a dedicated idle job on the nodes used and then subtracting it from the total measured energy.

There are multiple ways to capture energy consumption, which vary in granularity, accuracy, and accessibility:

1. Hardware Counters (Recommended):

1.1. Examples: Intel RAPL (CPU), NVIDIA's NVML library or ROCm-SMI for AMD (GPU).

1.2. Advantages: High resolution, workload-specific, widely available on modern HPC systems.

1.3. Limitations: May not capture all auxiliary components (memory, network, I/O), and some sites restrict user-level access.

2. IPMI (Baseboard Management Controller):

Provides node-level energy and power data collected by the system's management controller.

2.1. Advantages: Captures a wider range of components than RAPL, offering node-level granularity.

2.2. Limitations: Lower temporal resolution, potential delays in reporting, and sometimes limited user access.

3. Scheduler-level metrics:

Energy consumption data reported by job schedulers such as SLURM or LSF. The source of the data and, therefore, measurement resolution (temporal and spatial) depend on the system configuration. Some centres have the scheduler configured so that it reports the values from the Hardware Counters, which is the preferred approach.

4. Platform-level benchmarks:

Global energy efficiency metrics from rankings such as Top500, HPCG, or Green500, usually expressed in GFLOP/Watt from benchmark runs (e.g., Linpack). A possible approximation is to assume that the energy consumed by a climate simulation is proportional to the total power of the system as reported in these benchmarks. However, these benchmarks provide system-wide averages and are not representative of actual model workloads. They can be used as a rough reference when no better data are available, but the measurement fidelity is low (see [A power-measurement methodology for large-scale, high-performance computing](#)).

5. Monitoring tools: tools such as EAR (Energy-Aware Runtime), MERIC, LIKWID, Countdown, or ClusterCockpit, which may provide more detailed or continuous energy profiling. We do not

enforce which one to use as long as the source of the data is known and mentioned along with the measurements.

Facilitating energy profiling

To help modelling groups identify and use the energy profilers available on their target HPC systems, we offer the **Portable Power Locality** (pwrloc) tool. <https://github.com/BSC-ES/pwrloc>

- pwrloc acts as an interface to multiple energy profiling backends and helps users automatically detect what energy measurement options are available on a given machine.
- It supports several profiling tools commonly found on HPC systems, such as SLURM, Perf, PAPI, NVML, and rocm-smi.
- Different systems expose different combinations of these profilers. pwrloc simplifies discovery and selection, enabling users to identify the most suitable energy measurement backend for their setup without requiring new installations or administrator intervention.